

Stemming Algorithm optimization using big data analytics tools

M. BOUGAR¹, Dr, EL. ZIYATI²,
RITM LABORATORY EST/ENSEM, University Hassan II
Casablanca, Morocco
Marieme.bougar7@gmail.com¹, Ziyati@gmail.com²

Abstract: With the exploitation of BIG DATA this article focuses, from a technical point of view, on the optimization of algorithms for pre-processing and classification of Big Data. Indeed, the massive amount of data produced in the world reaches such large volumes that it is undeniably impossible to analyze them manually without the help of adequate technology and statistical tools. As a result, we have chosen to exploit the open-source softwares HADOOP and SPARK. This work is interested in the Arabic language because we wanted to give our language even more interest in the world of scientific research in the face of the universal English language. This work created the optimizations of powerful algorithms for the preprocessing and classification of data in Arabic, as well as a comparative study to choose the best Big Data technological tools according to one's need.

Key words: BIG DATA, Preprocessing, classification, Stemming, HADOOP, SPARK

I. INTRODUCTION

Arabic is the mother tongue of more than 400 million people and ranks seventh among Internet users in 2010 [1]. Arabic content on the Web has increased in volume, especially after the advent of social media. There are more than 6.5 million Arab Internet users generating 10.8 million tweets per day [2]. As a result, information-seeking systems for Arabic languages are becoming increasingly sophisticated and their evaluation is an important guide in the field of scientific research.

The challenge remains that the Arabic language is perceived as difficult. Indeed, derivative forms are sometimes irregular and flexed, spelling is different for certain words, writing differs from certain combinations of characters, short and long vowels and the richness of affixes in words [3] [4]. In addition, it is also necessary to consider many specification points of Arabic words, such as unstructured forms, words that spell differently depending on the context and specification of diacritics [6], which have led to the emergence of many approaches to overcome its challenges and address the Arabic language [7] [8], and not missing to mention the different dialects.

In this work, we address the challenge of big data for analytics, which require an efficient system that can manage the elasticity and scalability of data, especially the speed and efficiency that the MapReduce model offers. Indeed, it is considered one of the wisest choices for the analysis of large data [5].

We have reproduced and optimized Khoja Stemmer with the Apache Hadoop Framework for word manipulation, storage and derivation. Yahoo developed Hadoop, an open source framework of the MapReduce system, to process several terabytes of data on as many as 10,000 cores. Hadoop is a distributed and scalable computing framework, as well as a powerful distributed storage and computer hardware tool for a much less expensive system [9].

The aim of this work is to analyze the results obtained using Spark on Hadoop, and to expose all possible synergies between the two Framework and their respective benefits. This completes our Stemmer Khoja optimization process and keeps the results provided by the essential algorithm in terms of the accuracy of the basic words output. This minimizes the running time and use of the hardware by implementing the clustering approach.

Towards the end of this two-part work, one dedicated to the comparison of the two Frameworks and another part for the implementation of Spark on Hadoop, a clear perception is designed to benefit from the characteristics and performance of both Frameworks. The results of our work also include renditions on the consumption aspect of CPU and memory, as well as the logical side of parallelism minimizing the execution time parameter.

The aim of this research is to propose an optimized algorithm based on the Khoja Stemmer, implementing existing storage principles and computational models to improve the performance and accuracy of classified outputs of the roots of Arabic words inputted into this mechanism. Several Stemmers have been selected to enter into this research work such as Khoja based on the roots of words, and the Light Stemmers.

Our algorithms can be applied to natural language processing areas and error detection for large volumes of data for specific analysis or classification purposes.

II. STEMMING ALGORITHMS:

Stemming's algorithm, or the "Stemmer," has three main objectives:

The first is to group words according to their subject. Many words are derivatives of the same root and we consider them to belong to the same concept. For example: investigation, investigation, investigator. These derivations are generated by affixes (prefixes, infixes, suffixes). In general, and more specifically in English, only suffixes are considered, because prefixes and infixes change the meaning of the word, which leads to errors of poor determination of the subject.

Some exceptions to this rule occur in very bending languages such as German and Dutch, or in documents belonging to specific themes, such as medicine or chemistry, where prefixes and suffixes retain the concept of the word. Of these suffixes, two types of diversions can be considered. In the first case, inflection derivations reflect grammatical information related to sex, number, or time. These derivations do not cause a change in the part of the speech of the original word, that is, the linguistic category of the word (name, verb or adjective), nor in its meaning. On the contrary, derivative suffixes create new words based on an existing word, with which it shares meaning or not (for example, words ending with -IZE, -ATION, -SHIP). By eliminating these suffixes from a derived word, we get its stem, which is almost its morphological root, and then we can identify thematically related words by matching their stems.

The second objective of a stem is directly related to the information-finding process, because having the words rods improves certain phases of this process. These include the possibility of indexing documents according to their themes, since their terms are grouped by rods (which are similar to concepts), or the widening of a query to obtain more and more accurate results.

Extending the query allows you to refine it by replacing the terms it contains with their related topics that are also present in the collection, or by adding these topics to the original query. This can be done automatically and transparently for users, or the system can offer users one or more improved query formulations, allowing them to decide whether one of them is more specific and better defines their needs. Even if the extension of the interactive query is better in principle, because the user has better feedback on what is happening, it generally can not be done directly with the result of the stem, because the stems are only incomprehensible by humans.

The confusion of words sharing the same root results in a reduction of the dictionary to be taken into account in the process, because the entire vocabulary contained in the collection of untreated input documents can be reduced to a set of subjects or roots. This leads to a reduction in the space needed to store the structures used by an information search system (such as the document terms index). This also reduces the system's computational load.

III. WHY IS ARABIC A CHALLENGE?

Arabic is a Semitic language, a linguistic family that also includes Hebrew, Aramaic and Amharic. It is estimated that there are about four hundred million first-language speakers of Arabic [11] [12]. It is their mother tongue or their second language. As this is the language of the religious teaching of Islam, many other speakers from different nations have a passive knowledge of the language. Arabic is also one of the six official languages of the United Nations and the fifth most used language in the world [10] [36].

Phrases in Arabic are delineated by dots, dashes and commas, while words are separated by spaces and other punctuation marks. Arabic writing is written from right to left, while Arabic numerals are written and read from left to right. Arabic writing consists of two types of symbols [11] [14]: letters and diacritics (also known as short vowels), which are certain spelling symbols, usually added to disambiguate Arabic words. Al-Salamah [10] stated that the Arabic alphabet has 28 letters and that, unlike English, there are no capital letters and lower case for Arabic letters. An additional character, which is the HAMZA (ء), has also been added, but it is generally not classified as the 29th letter.

Arabic words are divided into three parts: names including adjectives and adverbs, then verbs, and particles. In Arabic, particles are attached to verbs and names. The words in Arabic are either masculine or feminine. The feminine is often formed differently from the masculine, for example ' and ل, which means respectively: unique (female) mistress, unique (male) teacher.

The same characteristic also appears in the names and verbs in literary Arabic to indicate the number (singular, double to describe two entities, and the plural) as in معلمة et معلم.

Arabic has a complex morphology. Its diversion system is based on 10,000 independent roots [38]. The roots in Arabic are usually built from 3 consonants (triliterals) and it is possible that 4 consonants (quad-literal) or 5 consonants (pent-literal) are used. Of the 10,000 roots, only about 1,200 are still used in modern Arabic vocabulary [15].

Words are formed by widening the root with affixes using well-known morphological patterns (sometimes called measurements) [10] [16].

Words and morphological variations are derived from roots using patterns. Grammatically, the main motif, which corresponds to the trilateral root, is the pattern. More regular patterns, adhering to well-known morphological rules, may be derived from the main motif.

Different types of affixes can be added to derived pattern words to build a more complex structure. Defined articles, such as conjunctions, particles and other prefixes can be added at the beginning of the word, while suffixes can be added at the end. For example, the word **لنعلّمهم** - which means: we will teach them, can be broken down as follows: (antefix: ل, prefix: ن, root: علم, and postfix: هم). Kadri and Nie [17] have identified an important research that amply explains the affixes used in the Arabic language.

Unconstitutionals, whether separated or not, are usually prepositions added at the beginning of words before prefixes. Prefixes are attached to illustrate forms of verbs in future time and imperative, and usually consist of one, two or three letters. The suffixes are added to indicate sex and number, for example in the female double and the male plural.

Postfixes are used to indicate pronouns and to represent the object. Usually, this morphology is used to create verbal and nominal sentences.

Arabic affixes may also include clitics, which have been used in the proposed stems and can be proclitic or enclitic depending on their location in the words. These are morphemes that have the syntactic characteristics of one word but are morphologically related to others [18]. Thus, the clicks are attached to the beginning or end of the words. These clitics include certain prepositions, defined articles, conjunctions, possessive pronouns, particles and pronouns. Examples of clitics are the letters pronounced as (KAF) and pronounced as (FAA), which mean respectively as and then.

Arabic adjectives are considered names. Thus, the different forms that can be derived from the adjective (مزارع) meaning "farmer" according to their two grammatical forms may include words such as: (مزارعة) for the singular feminine in nominative cases, (مزارعان) for the double male in the nominative case, (مزارعين) for the male, (مزارعتان) for the female double in the nominative case, (مزارعتين) for the female double etc....

Morphology adds a degree of ambiguity and difficulty, making the exact keyword matching mechanism insufficient to extract words. Morphological ambiguity may appear in several cases. For example, clitics may accidentally produce homogeneous form (the same word with two or more different meanings) with another complete word [10] [11] [19][29]. For example, the word (علم) can be attached to the clitic ي (to construct the word **علمي**) which is homographic with the word "scientific."

In addition, Arabic grammar contributes to morphological ambiguity. According to some arabic grammar rules, vowels may be removed from the roots. The letter of the vowels in Arabic consists of three letters: ALIF, YAA and WAW (أ، ي، و). These letters have different rules, which do not follow the system derived from Arabic, and make

them very variable. For example, the last letter YAA is deleted in a word such as (امشي) meaning "goes," which gives(امش), if that verb appears in an imperative form.

In addition to its complex morphology, Arabic also has an overly complex type of plural called "broken plural." Plurals in Arabic do not obey morphological rules.

Broken plurals make up 10% of Arabic texts and 41% of plurals [10] [20]. The plural in Arabic indicates any number greater than two; for two, it's double.

The term "broken" means that the plural form does not resemble the original singular form. For example, the plural of the word(نهر)meaning "river" is(أنهار)"rivers." In simple cases of broken plurals, the new inflected plural contains some letters common to the singular form, as in the previous example. But in many cases, the plural is totally different from the original word, for example, the plural of the word (إمراة) is (نساء), keeping no letter from the root.

Another challenge, which are simply caused by the Arabic letters ALIF with its various forms (ا , إ , آ) . In most cases, one of this letter is modified or abandoned [21].

A. Focus on the Khoja Stemmer algorithm

Khoja Stemmer has been used by numerous researches to analyze the Arabic text, at the pre-processing and filtering stage of the text, in particular to remove a stop word. Khoja Stemmer eliminates diacritics and the longest prefix. The Stemmer manages punctuation characters, diacritic characters, a large number of stop words and a defined article. The Khoja Stemmer proceeds as shown in Figure 1.

Khoja's Stemming algorithm removes the longest suffix and prefix. Then, the remaining word is compared to verbal and nominative models. To extract the root, it is based on a list of all diacritic signs, punctuation marks, defined articles and keywords.

KHOJA algorithm

1. remove diacritic signs
2. Delete: empty word, punctuation and numbers.
3. Delete the article defined by
4. Remove the separable conjunction
5. remove suffixes
6. remove the prefix
7. Match the results with a list of patterns: if the match is found, extract the characters from the pattern that the root represents. Compare the extracted root with a list of known valid roots.
8. Replace the letters of the week with.
9. Replace all hamza instances with a.
10. The roots of two letters are checked to see if they should contain a double sign. If this is the case, the sign is added to the root

Figure 1 KHOJA algorithm

B. Conclusion

While not all researchers agree on the pros and cons of using Stemming as a process for seeking information in general terms, many agree on its benefits in specific contexts, when language is highly inflected, when documents are short or when data storage space is limited. Some researchers also argue that the nature of the documents can influence the performance and accuracy of the Stemmer.

Despite the fact that many researchers have studied this field for many years, a few questions remain open: how to evaluate a Stemming independently of the information-seeking process; how a Stemming improves the search for information in terms of speed. For these reasons, we have decided to try to answer these unknowns.

IV. LES BIG DATA:

A. Big data analytics tools

In the following, we have two ways of processing data. The first is to use the Mapreduce Framework Hadoop batch mode, the second is the streaming mode, it is a real-time processing, using Spark for data processing.

1) Hadoop

Apache HADOOP is a framework used to develop data processing applications that are run in a distributed computing environment. Similar to data residing in a local file system of a personal computer system, in Hadoop, the data resides in a distributed file system that is called Hadoop distributed file system. The processing model is based on the concept of "Data Locality," in which the calculation logic is sent to a group of nodes (servers) containing data.

This logic of calculation is nothing more than a compiled version of a program written in a high-level language, such as Java. Such a program processes data stored in Hadoop HDFS. Applications built with HADOOP are run on large datasets in widely available core computer groups. They are mainly useful for getting greater computing power at low cost. The computational cluster consists of a set of multiple processing units (storage disk - processor) that are connected to each other and act as a single system.

Figure 2: Clusters HADOOP2

Apache Hadoop consists of two sub-projects [23]:

1. Hadoop MapReduce: MapReduce (Figure 2) is a computational model and writing software framework that is performed on Hadoop. These MapReduce programs are capable of processing massive data in parallel on large clusters of computational nodes.
2. HDFS (Hadoop Distributed File System): HDFS(Figure 2) handles the storage part of Hadoop applications. MapReduce applications consume HDFS data. HDFS creates multiple replicas of data blocks and distributes them on cluster computing nodes [30]. This distribution allows for a reliable and extremely fast data management system in calculations.

HADOOP installation

To install HADOOP [80] we used the version (2.6) in "SINGLE NODE INSTALLATION" mode on UBUNTU 14.04 LTS (32 bit).

Below we describe the various stages of installation and implementation of this architecture

Step 1: Open the terminal using the next keyboard key combination (ctrl-alt-t), then write the next command
marie@localhost sudo apt-get update

Step 2: \$marie@localhost sudo apt-get upgrade

Étape 3 : marie@localhost\$ sudo apt-get install openssh-server

Step 4: First check whether the jdk (java set up) is installed on the machine or not. To open the terminal we use (ctrl at-t) and then write the following command: marie@localhost\$java-version (If Java is already installed do not run step 5).

Step 5: to install java you must write the following command: `marie@localhost$ sudo -get install openjdk-7-jdk`
`marie@localhost$ java -version` NOTER THAT: you will have a message that JAVA 1.7 VERSION is successfully installed, the jdk will be installed in the file `/usr/lib/jvm/java-7-openjdk-i386`

Step 6: Download Hadoop with the following command `marie@localhost$ wget`
`http://mirrors.sonic.net/apache/Hadoop/common/Hadoop-2.6.0/Hadoop-2.6.0.tar.gz` (then put the downloaded folder in the following folder: `/usr/local` file (this means that Hadoop is installed in the directory `/usr/local`) NOTE: you can install Hadoop wherever you want. `marie@localhost$ sudo tar -zxvf /Downloads/Hadoop-2.6.0.tar.gz -C /usr/local;`

Note: to extract Hadoop `Hadoop-2.6.0.tar.gz` from the repertoire: `/usr/local;marie@localhost$ sudo mv`
`/usr/local/Hadoop-2.6.0 /usr/local/Hadoop;` Note: to rename the f file: `marie@localhost$ sudo chown -R marie`
`/usr/local/Hadoop;`

Step 7: Add a group and a Hadoop user: `$marie@localhost$ sudo addgroup Hadoop;` `marie@localhost$ sudo adduser`
`--ingroup Hadoop marie;(marie is our user name Hadoop) marie@localhost$ sudo adduser marie sudo;`

Step 8: Run the SSH certificate and generate your keys: `marie@localhost$ ssh-keygen -t rsa -P"`
`marie@localhost$ cat .ssh/id_rsa.pub .ssh/authorized_keys`

Step 9: Get your IP address `marie@localhost ifconfig marie@localhost$ sudo gedit /etc/hosts;` `marie@localhost$`
`sudo gedit /etc/hostname;` `marie@localhost$ ssh localhost;` Note: restart computer (`$marie@localhost sudo reboot`)

Step 10: Open the bashrc file and write the following code for Hadoop `marie@localhost$ sudo nano ~/.bashrc`
`marie@localhost$ source ~/.bashrc:`

```
export JAVA_HOME=/usr/lib/jvm/java-7-openjdk-i386 export HADOOP_INSTALL=/usr/local/Hadoop export
PATH=marie@localhost$PATH:marie@localhost$HADOOP_INSTALL/bin export
PATH=marie@localhost$PATH:marie@localhost$HADOOP_INSTALL/sbin export
HADOOP_MAPRED_HOME=marie@localhost$HADOOP_INSTALL export
HADOOP_COMMON_HOME=marie@localhost$HADOOP_INSTALL export
HADOOP_HDFS_HOME=marie@localhost$HADOOP_INSTALL export
YARN_HOME=marie@localhost$HADOOP_INSTALL export
HADOOP_COMMON_LIB_NATIVE_DIR=marie@localhost$HADOOP_HOME/lib/native export
JAVA_LIBRARY_PATH=marie@localhost$HADOOP_HOME/lib/native export HADOOP_OPTS="-
Djava.library.path"=marie@localhost$HADOOP_INSTALL/lib
```

(Finally note that `JAVA_HOME` contains the path of my jdk and `/usr/lib/jvm/java-7-openjdk-i386`
`HADOOP_INSTALL` is the path where Hadoop is installed on my computer, Hadoop is installed in `/usr/local/Hadoop`)

Step 10: set up the following xml files: `marie@localhost$ cd /usr/local/Hadoop/etc/Hadoop` Edit `core-site.xml:`
`marie@localhost$ sudo gedit core-site.xml` write: `fs.default.name hdfs://localhost:9000`

Step 10.1: set up `hdfs-site.xml` `marie@localhost sudo gedit hdfs-site.xml` write on the following lines: `dfs.replication 1`
`dfs.permissions false`

Step 10.2: set up `mapred-site.xml` NOTE: currently in the folder: `/usr/local/Hadoop/etc/Hadoop` , the `mapred-site.xml` file is not present. On the other hand the `mapred-site.xml.template` file is available, so you have to convert this file from `mapred-site.xml.template` to `mapred-site.xml` using the command `CONVERT mapred-site.xml.template at mapred-site.xml` `marie@localhost$ mv mapred-site.xml.mapred-mapred-site.xml`

Étape 10.3 : change `mapred-site.xml` file `marie@localhost$ sudo nano mapred-site.xml` write down following lines
`mapred.job.tracker localhost:9001`

Step 10.4: set up the file `Hadoop-env.sh` `marie@localhost$ sudo nano Hadoop-env.sh` `/usr/lib/jvm/java-7-openjdk-i386` (just write this path in `JAVA_HOME`) my `jdk` is installed in `/usr/lib/jvm/java-7-openjdk-i386`)

Step 11: FORMATER NAMENODE using the following command on the terminal: `cd /usr/local/Hadoop/bin` then type the command: `marie@localhost$ Hadoop namenode -format`

Step 12: Restart all DEMONS `$marie@localhost start-all.sh`

Step 13: Check that all DEMONS are in RUNNING status to write the following command: `marie@localhost$ jps` (if all the demons are present you have successfully installed your Hadoop)

Figure 3: The MAPREDUCE Model3

Inputs and outputs

The MapReduce model (Figure 3) works exclusively on key, value pairs, i.e. they are seen at the entrance to the Job as a set of 'key', value-for-money' pairs and produces a set of key, valueable pairs like job exit, possibly of different types.

Key and value classes must be seable by the model and must therefore implement an inscriptible interface. In addition, key classes must implement the `WritableComparable` interface to make it easier for the model to sort.

Types of entry and exit of a MapReduce job:

(Entry) - `v1, v1 - map - 'lt'k2, v2 - combine - -k2, v2 - reduce --t'3, v3`

execution

To run the java code:

- Copy the code into a java file. Execute the following commands.
- Configure environment variables: `export JAVA_HOME=/usr/java/default` `export PATH=marie@localhost${JAVA_HOME}/bin:marie@localhost${PATH}` `export HADOOP_CLASSPATH=marie@localhost${JAVA_HOME}/lib/tools.jar`
- Compile Name.java and create jar: `$marie@localhost bin/Hadoop com.sun.tools.javac.Main Name.java marie@localhost$ jar cf wc.jar Nom-.class`

Make sure that:

- `/user/marie/Name/input` - the input path exists in HDFS
- `/user/marie/wordcount/output` - output path exists in HDFS
- To run any code or test: `marie@localhost$ bin/Hadoop jar file.jar /user/marie/contact/user/user/marie/name/output`

The MapReduce programming model includes two functions, `map ()` and `reduce ()`. Users can implement their own processing logic by providing a custom `map ()` and `reduce ()` function. The `map` function takes a key/entry value pair and creates a list of key/intermediate pairs. MapReduce's execution system groups all intermediate pairs according to intermediate keys and transmits them to the `reduce` function `()` to obtain the final results [86].

Map Reduce can be divided into two steps:

- a) The mapped key/entry value pairs to a set of key/intermediate-value pairs. Maps are the individual tasks that turn input records into intermediate records. Processed intermediate records do not need to be the same type as input records. A given input pair can map on zero or several output pairs.
- b) Reducator Steps: The gearbox has three main steps: mix, sort and shrink.
 1. Random play: Random playback is a step on intermediate data, used to combine all values in the key associated set. After that, there will be no more duplicate keys in the intermediate data.
 2. Sorting: All intermediate keys on a single node will be automatically sorted before being presented to the gearbox. The sorting is done thanks to the Box class. Random reading and sorting phase at the same time; When extracting the exit of the card, they must be merged.
 3. Streamline: Provide shuffle output data and sort the maapper. Reduce at this stage for each pair to value list as long as a group entry.

2) *Apache Spark Perspective*

Apache Spark is a general-purpose cluster computing engine, very fast and reliable. This system provides application programming interfaces in various programming languages such as Java, Python, Scala.

Spark is an Apache cluster computing system with incubator status. This tool specializes in making data analysis faster, both for running programs and for writing data. Spark supports memory computing, allowing it to query data much faster than disk-based engines like Hadoop. It also offers a general execution model that can optimize an arbitrary operator graph. Initially, the system was developed at Berkeley University as a research project and acquired incubator status in Apache in June 2013 [5].

In general, Spark is an advanced and high-performance Upgrade from Hadoop to improve Hadoop's advanced analytics capability. The functions of the Spark engine are very advanced and different from those of Hadoop. The Spark engine is developed for memory processing as well as disk processing. This memory processing capability makes it much faster than any traditional data processing engine. For example, the project's sensors report that logistic regression in Spark is 100 times faster than in Hadoop MapReduce [25].

This system also provides many impressive high-level tools such as the MLib machine learning tool, structured data processing, Spark SQL, graphics processing taken GraphX, the flow processing engine called Spark Streaming, and Shark for the quick interactive question device [26]. This is shown in Figure 8.

Spark Components

The following illustration shows the different components of Spark.

Figure 4: SPARK Framework4

- Spark Core is the underlying general performance of the engine for the Sparks platform that all other features benefit from it It provides in memory the calculation and referencing of data sets in storage systems.
- Spark SQL is a component that is added to Spark Core. It introduces a new data abstraction called SchemaRDD, which provides support for structured and semi-structured data.
- Spark Streaming leverages Spark Core's speed and programming capability to stream analysis. It ingests data in mini batches and performs RDD (Resilient Distributed Datasets) transformations on these mini-batches of data.

- MLlib is a machine learning bookstore distributed on Spark because of spark's distributed memory-based architecture. According to benchmarks, between MLlib developments with ALS (ALS: Alternating Least Squares) implementations, Spark MLlib is nine times faster than Hadoop's Apache Mahout-based version.

GraphX

- GraphX is a graphics processing distributed above Spark. It provides an API expressing graphic calculations to model user-defined graphs using Pregel abstraction. It also provides an optimized execution time for this abstraction.

3) *Spark built on Hadoop*

There are three ways to deploy Spark [32], explained below and illustrated in Figure 13.

- Standalone: Spark's stand-alone deployment means that Spark occupies HDFS [9] (Hadoop Distributed File System) and space is allocated for HDFS, explicitly. Here, Spark and MapReduce work side by side to cover all of Spark's jobs on the cluster. This mode is used when resources are allocated statically on the cluster or on a subset of machines in a Hadoop cluster. Spark can be run in parallel with Hadoop MapReduce, so the user can perform arbitrary tasks on his HDFS data. This deployment makes it simple for many Hadoop 1.x users.
- Hadoop Yarn: The deployment of Hadoop Yarn [111] [28] means that Spark operates on Yarn without pre-installation or access to the required root. This allows Spark to be integrated into the Hadoop or Hadoop Battery ecosystem. This mode makes it easy for Hadoop users to integrate Spark. It allows you to take full advantage of Spark, as well as other components running on Spark. Hadoop users have the option to run Sparks on their Hadoop wire. Even users who already use the Hadoop wire easily integrate Spark. There are no requirements such as pre-installation or administrator access.
- Spark in MapReduce (SIMR): Spark in MapReduce is used to launch Spark work on stand-alone deployment. With SIMR, the user can launch Spark and use his shell without any administrative access. In addition to stand-alone deployment, Hadoop users who do not yet use YARN can switch to SIMR. We can use this mode to start work in MapReduce.

Figure 5: Sparks cluster architecture.5

4) Comparison of Mapreduce and Spark

Below is a summary of comparative studies based on the parameters of Big Data's analytics tools [24] [27] [31]. We try to understand and reproduce this comparison in order to construct a succinct comparison and allow the reader to make a first decision on the choice of tool, and for this proposed topic, we facilitate applications for the algorithm of Stemming in parallel.

Table 1: Comparison Spark vs Hadoop1

Mapreduce	Spark
MapReduce is ineffective for multi-pass applications	Spark allows large amounts of data to be processed in input.
Need to share over multiple low-latency data	Use for online machines and enable real-time analysis
Parallel operation.	
Intermediate data/results are stored more slowly on the hard drive	Compared to Hadoop, the speed can be increased up to 100 times for iterative operations, as the data/intermediate results are preserved in the memory.
Mainly a batch processing engine	Spark as a batch processing engine also includes Spark Streaming for streaming data processing, MLLib GraphX for machine learning.
Less memory needs	Memory requirements are higher. This degrades performance when data doesn't fit in memory
Each mapping task generates data in a Key, value union. The output is stored in the Buffer Cache instead of writing on the disk.	The exit from the mapping side was written in the buffer cache. It is up to the operating system to decide whether the data can be stored in the buffer cache or should be stored.

بِسْمِ اللّٰهِ الرَّحْمٰنِ الرَّحِیْمِ
الْحَمْدُ لِلّٰهِ رَبِّ الْعٰلَمِیْنَ
الرَّحْمٰنِ الرَّحِیْمِ
مٰلِكِ یَوْمِ الدِّیْنِ
اِنَّكَ تَعْلَمُ سِرِّیْنَ
اِنَّكَ تَعْلَمُ الْغُیْبَیْنَ
اِنَّكَ تَعْلَمُ الْغُیْبَیْنَ
سِرِّیْنَ
بِسْمِ اللّٰهِ الرَّحْمٰنِ الرَّحِیْمِ
ذٰلِكَ الْكِتٰبُ لَا رَیْبَ فِیْهِ هُدًى لِّلْمُتَّقِیْنَ
الَّذِیْنَ یُؤْمِنُونَ بِالْغَیْبِ وَیُقِیْمُونَ الصَّلٰةَ وَمِمَّا رَزَقْنٰهُمْ یُنْفِقُونَ
وَالَّذِیْنَ یُؤْمِنُونَ بِمَا اُنزِلَ اِلَیْكَ وَمَا اُنزِلَ مِنْ قَبْلِكَ وَیَالَاخِرَةَ هُمْ یُؤْفِقُونَ
اُولٰٓئِكَ عَلٰی كُلِّ شَیْءٍ حٰكِمُونَ
اِنَّ الَّذِیْنَ كَفَرُوْا سَوَآءٌ عَلَیْهِمْ اَلَّذَلٰیْمُ اَمْ لَمْ یَلِدُوْا اَمْ لَمْ یَكُنْ لَهُمْ اَرْحَامٌ اَمْ لَمْ یَكُنْ لَهُمْ اَعْمٰلٌ
عَلٰی اللّٰهِ فَاُولٰٓئِكَ سَوَآءٌ عَلَیْهِمْ اَلَّذَلٰیْمُ
وَمِنَ النَّاسِ مَنْ یَكُوْلُ اٰمٰنًا بِاللّٰهِ وَیَالْتِیْمًا بِالْآخِرِ وَمَا هُمْ بِمُؤْمِنِیْنَ
یَخٰرِفُونَ اللّٰهَ وَالَّذِیْنَ اٰمَنُوْا وَمَا یَخْدَعُونَ اِلَّا اَنْفُسَهُمْ وَمَا یَشْعُرُونَ
فِیْ قُلُوْبِهِمْ مَّرَدٌ فَاذْكُرْهُمۡ اللّٰهُ مَرَّةً وَّحَدِیْثًا وَلَهُمْ عَذَابٌ اَلِیْمٌ
وَإِذَا قِیْلَ لَهُمْ لَا تُعْبَدُوْا فِی الْاَرْضِ قَالُوْا اِنَّمَا نَحْنُ مُتَّبِعُوْنَ
اَلَّذِیْنَ كَفَرُوْا وَكُنَّا لَا نَشْعُرُ
وَإِذَا قِیْلَ لَهُمْ اٰمِنُوْا كَمَا اٰمَنَ النَّاسُ قَالُوْا اَلَّذِیْنَ اٰمَنُوْا كَمَا اٰمَنَ السُّفٰهَاءُ وَكُنَّا لَا نَعْلَمُ
وَإِذَا قِیْلَ لَهُمْ اٰمِنُوْا قَالُوْا اِنَّمَا نَحْنُ مُتَّبِعُوْنَ
اِنَّ اللّٰهَ یَسْتَهْزِئُ بِهٖمْ وَیَعَذَّبُہُمْ فِیْ طَعٰنِیْمٍ یَّخْتَمُوْنَ
اُولٰٓئِكَ الَّذِیْنَ اَشْرٰوْا الْبِلَادَ بِالْاَهْلِیِّیْمِیْنَ
مَنْعَلَمٌ كَمَثَلِ الَّذِیْ اَسْتَوْتَدُّ نَارًا فَلَئِمَّا اَضَاءَتْ مَا حَوْلَهَا ذَمَّ اللّٰهُ بِسُوْرِمِهِمْ وَتَرَکَهُمْ فِیْ طُلُمَاتٍ لَا یُبْصَرُوْنَ
مِمْ نَحْمٌ غُیْرُ فِیْہُمْ لَا یَرْجِعُوْنَ

Figure 6: Extract of the data (coran) input from our algorithms.6

V. OUR ALGORITHMS: RESULTS, AND MODEL

A. Study of the existing algorithm

1) KHOJA Algorithm

The KHOJA Stemmer algorithm is developed in java and available online:[<http://zeus.cs.pacificu.edu/shereen/research.htm>], as well as other versions taken up by researchers.

We had in our disposal:

- The MAIN class ARABICStemmer in java (Main Class).
- The Stemmer Class in java: containing the feature that treats the entire Khoja Stemmer process
- Gui Classes, containing the development of the graphical interface (Figure 7)
- The folder Stemmer Files building the data dictionary necessary for the conversion of characters and words, Khoja is based on the dictionary approach.

Figure 7 : Graphic interface of Khoja Stemmer

This interface contains several functions, mainly cited:

- Open: Button to load the desired document.
- Stem: Button to start Stemming treatment,
- Statistics: Button to view results measuring the accuracy of the roots extracted from the words provided on the basis
- Save as: Button to download and save the results of the stemming.

Figure 8: Khoja Stemmer's Approach⁷

2) Preliminary results

Examples of results are presented in Table 2, which presents different information: word, radical, type, prefix, affix and suffix. Its elements are important for identifying words, here is some type of information provided by the algorithm.

Table 2: Results provided by the Stemmer Khoja Algorithm.2

Word	Stem	Type	Pattern	Préfix	affix	suffix
from	from	Stop WORD	Null	Null	Null	Null
U,000	Uterus	Root	make	the	Null	nun
owner	possess	Root	make	Null	alif	Null

For a unit test performed on a word set that reaches 82624 words, the result displayed is 98.87%.

3) Lucene light Stemmer

In Figure 8.1 we present Lucene's algorithm [22] which is an Apache Arab Stemmer.

1. Normaliser le mot :

- 1.1 Supprimer les diacritiques.
- 1.2 Remplacer آ إ ؤ with ا.
- 1.3 Remplacer ة with ه.
- 1.4 Remplacer ي with ي.
- 1.5 Finir un re-process d'élimination des diacritiques

2 Stemming :

- 2.1 Eliminer les préfixes : وال ، فال ، كال ، بال ، تل ، و.
- 2.2 Eliminer les suffixes : ها ، ان ، ات ، ون ، ين ، ية ، ه ي :

Figure 8.1: Light Stemmer Lucene algorithm8

4) Advantage of a Light Stemmer's process

The main idea of using light Stemmer is that many word variants do not have similar meanings or semantics. However, these word variants are generated from the same root.

Thus, root-based Stemming algorithms affect the meaning of words. The Light Stemming aims to improve classification performance while maintaining the true meaning of words. It certainly removes the prefixes and suffixes

of the word instead of seeking to extract the original root, for example the Arabic words (المكتبة الكاتب الكتاب) which mean (the library, the book, the writer) respectively, belong to the same root (كتب) although they have not the same meaning. Thus, the Lucene's approach is to keep the original meaning of the word. As a result of Lucerne, the new results will match the word (الكتاب) which means (the book) to (كتاب) (which means (the book)).

5) The Mapreduce Computing Model

Map() is the first step in the MapReduce algorithm. It takes input tasks and divides them into smaller sub-tasks. The release of this Mapping function is a set of pairs of keys and values (key, value).

The reduction step takes a list of outputs from the Mapping function and performs these two sub-steps on each key-value pair.

Hadoop's Framework MapReduce uses a distributed file system to read and write its data. Hadoop MapReduce uses the Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS), as well as file system. Therefore, the entry/exit performance of a Hadoop MapReduce job is closely dependent on HDFS.

The idea of our PSA algorithm and to use this model properly and admit that the key and the word is referred to in the same way and this in order to keep track of the original word to be milled in the Stemmer that will be highlighted in the output. Thus a stage pair of Mapping is defined for example as follows (الرحمن, الرحمن), then at the intermediate phase called shuffling() sets of pairs will be assembled by common key finally in the stage of the reduce function() or the algorithm Khoja will be applied to get out the roots of the corresponding words out a file of pairs (original word, word after stemming) is built.

Figure 9:9 MapReduce model applied to Khoja algorithm.

6) *PSA algorithm*

Figure10: Parallel Stemming Algorithm (PSA)

7) *Result and discussion*

This program takes as an entry a heavy text document of the Koran. The output is the original word, its root with the type of belonging. All results, as shown in the figures and tables below, are directed to a web page. Then we calculate the run time with parallel processing by implementing our method and without parallel treatment, the comparison with other Root-based Stemmer or light Stemmer shows an improvement in workload.

The application allows the user to view the algorithm classification from the fastest, the dashboard shows the size of the derivative document and gives permission to download the Word derived document.

Figure11: DASHBOARD web comparative PSA, Lucene, Khoja.

Figure 12 shows that PSA's run time increases linearly in volume, but for other algorithms, the graph grows exponentially, like Khoja's algorithm.

In conclusion, the new version of Stemmer's algorithm based on distributed treatment MapReduce, shows a remarkable improvement, especially when the volume increases, the PSA acts linearly instead of other algorithms that are parabolic or even exponential.

8) Implementation of Spark solutions

Clustering en Spark

It's always a misrepresentation that Spark replaces Hadoop, but it affects Hadoop's functionality. From the beginning, Spark reads data from HDFS (Hadoop Distributed File System) and writes data. Therefore, apache Spark is a Data Processing Engine based on Hadoop. It can support batch processing and data streaming. Therefore, running Spark on Hadoop can provide improved features and more features.

Apache Spark is a framework for a computation distributed in memory, flexible in terms of writing the Spark application and deploying it to clusters. Writing applications on Spark allows calculations to evolve by adding machines and running them in cluster mode (Figure 13). You can then expand your app locally and then deploy it to

Figure 12:10 Evolution PSA run time versus another Stemming algorithm.

multiple clusters without changing the lines of code.

Figure 13: STANDBY mode: Setting up Master/Slave architecture

Resilient Distributed Data Set (RDD)

Spark RDD (API-RDD) stands for Elastic Distributed Data Set. It is a collection of recording scores in playback alone. RDD is Spark's core data structure. It allows programmers to perform memory calculations on large clusters in a way that is tolerant of failures. As a result, the task is accelerated.

Spark made RDD available to users via an API developed in Scala (basic language), Java or Python. The datasets in the RDDs are represented as objects (class instances) and the transformations that are called to support the methods of these objects.

RDDs are collections of objects - basic elements of Spark that allow a calculation tolerant to failures and which are characterized by two main operations: transformations (map, reduce, filter ...) and actions (collect, count...) using filter and reduceByKey on RDD.

A RDD collection uses the cache to store RAM data for reuse, thus avoiding the disk data replication needed in Hadoop to ensure cluster availability. It is through this mechanism that you can provide high availability and tolerance to cluster failures.

In our implementation of the PSA algorithm with RDD (Figure 14), each line of the file (Holly Quran/Arabic Text) is read as an entire chain in RDD. Then the current line is divided into words that are put into a table generated by the "split" command. At the end of processing all lines. The order flatMap produces a table that includes all the tables generated in the division result. The final table is filtered to get only separate words. Each word is matched with a

Figure 14:11 PSA algorithm improved in Spark RDD context

key/value pair. Finally, the operation reduceByKey is used on the key/value pair to apply the function Stemming on the value of the words in order to generate the root out.

Not to mention that we specify in our Spark level code the URL of our Master Node implementation that we get via the address localhost:8080, in that same page also we can recover several information including the number of workers or Slaves we created and the number of Jobs executed.

9) Results and discussion

In this section we set out our results in terms of the accuracy of the root words, the time it takes to complete the various implementations chosen during the study phase, the consumption in terms of memory and finally the use of the CPU.

Figure 15: Evolution in time execution by file size¹²

As figure 15 shows, our algorithm using Spark makes our temporal function virtually nil.

Figure 16: Time run by 13HADOOP vs. SPARKfile.

The results obtained for the Standalone implementation mode (HDFS for file system) where our optimization of the PSA algorithm with the RDD design, and are represented by tables later.

The stick graph in (Figure 16) allows you to visualize the execution time achieved by deploying the two frames separately, so our architecture (Standalone mode) used for Spark gives important results in terms of reducing execution time.

Both Hadoop and Spark require high memory consumption (Figure 17), however Spark is performed to save the use of CPU (Figure 17), these results are explained by the fact that Hadoop rewrites the value of the key on the disk, while Spark's storage is in memory.

Figure 17:14Consumption of SPARK vs. HADOOP Memory and CPU

The consumption rates of resources memory are carefully recovered using the usual commands: free -m for globality, ps for the detail of processes.

Khoja
82624 words

Application
The following extensions are allowed : doc and txt
[import file](#) No file selected

Stemmed words

عشرة	عشر	Root
عشر	عشر	Root
عصا	عص	Root
عصا	عص	Root

display Following 7 5 words 10 words 20 words

PSA
82624 words

Ranking
Execution time

Name	Words	Time	
1 Spark	82624 words	1.425979 secondes	download
2 PSA	82624 words	2.747 secondes	download

click on the link to save the complete display as to download

Spark
82624 words

In addition, the use of the CPU is supervised thanks to the "top" surveillance command, standard for most systems, and which was of great use to us. Normally, the "top" command is used dynamically. At the start, a table appears with values that change dynamically depending on the activities of each process, we also trace the time of the release of the Stemming process allowed us to align the results at a specific moment T.

We chose to track our results in terms of execution time and stemming results through a web application (Figure 18) for form and facilitate analysis as we tackle a lot of tests, hence the mastery of managing the history in visual result capture and output file loading for consultation.

Table 4: Result 1- Time Performance Spark vs Hadoop3

Framework	File size	Number of words	Results in seconds
Hadoop	112 bytes	6	1.156
Spark	112 bytes	6	0,262955

Figure 18:15Return of PSA exit results (Hadoop/Spark)

Table 5: Result 2 -Time Execution Spark vs Hadoop4

Framework	File size	Number of words	Results in seconds
Hadoop	1.3 Mo	82624	2.747 sec
Spark	1.3 Mo	82624	1.425979 sec

Table 6: Result 3- Time Execution Spark vs Hadoop5

Framework	File size	Number of words	Results in seconds
Hadoop	3 Mo	165248	2.9 sec
Spark	3 Mo	165248	1.5 sec

Table 7: Result 4-time execution Spark vs Hadoop6

Framework	File size	Number of words	Results in seconds
Hadoop	6 Mo	415173	10 sec
Spark	6 Mo	415173	8 sec

The tables from 4 to 7, just consolidates the graph (figure 15) is shows in detail the number of words the size of the file and the number of seconds manifest at the end of the execution and the layout of the Output file. The running time is managed in the algorithms.

```
1 (بِسْمِ , بَسْمِ )
2 (اللّٰهُ , لِلّٰهِ )
3 (الرَّحْمٰنِ , رَحْمِ )
4 (الرَّحِيْمِ , رَحِيْمِ )
5 (الْحَمْدِ , حَمْدِ )
6 (لِلّٰهِ , لِلّٰهِ )
7 (رَبِّ , رَبِّ )
8 (الْعٰلَمِيْنَ , عَالِمِ )
9 (الرَّحْمٰنِ , رَحْمِ )
10 (الرَّحِيْمِ , رَحِيْمِ )
11 (عَالِيكَ , مَلِكِ )
12 (يَوْمِ , يَوْمِ )
13 (الَّذِيْنَ , دُوْنِ )
14 (اِيَّاكَ , اِيَّاكَ )
15 (تَعْبُدُ , تَعْبُدُ )
16 (وَاِيَّاكَ , اِيَّاكَ )
17 (تَسْتَعِيْنُ , تَسْتَعِيْنُ )
18 (اِهْدِنَا , اِهْدِنَا )
19 (الصِّرَاطَ , الصِّرَاطَ )
20 (الْمُسْتَقِيْمَ , قَوْمِ )
21 (صِرَاطَ , صِرَاطِ )
22 (الَّذِيْنَ , الَّذِيْنَ )
23 (اَنْعَمْتَ , اَنْعَمْتَ )
24 (عَلَيْهِمْ , عَلِيْ )
25 (عَوْرَ , عَوْرِ )
26 (الْمَغْمُوْمِ , عَصَبِ )
27 (عَلَيْهِمْ , عَلِيْ )
28 (وَلَا , وَلِيْ )
29 (الصَّالِحِيْنَ , ضَلِ )
30 (بِسْمِ , بَسْمِ )
31 (اللّٰهُ , لِلّٰهِ )
32 (الرَّحْمٰنِ , رَحْمِ )
33 (الرَّحِيْمِ , رَحِيْمِ )
34 (الْمِ , الْمِ )
35 (ذٰلِكَ , ذٰلِكَ )
36 (الْكِتٰبِ , كِتَابِ )
```

Figure 19: file example of algorithm OUTPUT

16

VI. CONCLUSION

The research carried out during this thesis has optimized data pre-processing algorithms and classified them as classification techniques, applied to the classical Arabic language, as we found in the early parts of this manuscript. Several factors give a major concern of researchers for the classification of the Arabic text.

We have detailed throughout the chapters of this report what has been done in the literature to help improve the performance of data pre-processing and analysis and to fully exploit high-performing tools in the context of high volume data processing.

Indeed, in the first chapter, after defining the problem and the need to improve the algorithms of "Stemming" in the research, we synthesized the solutions already used and the algorithms applied to meet this criterion and defined the main pillars. Then we will focus on the KHOJA algorithm, and add our contributions in this regard in the sense, where the goal was to improve the algorithm on the one hand under the framework of Hadoop and Spark and make very fluid the use of these two Framework for their algorithms likely to use large volume of input data.

The first contribution is an algorithm based on Hadoop capable of processing very large data that is Arabic text taking into account its processing complexity. We proposed the Qur'an in Corpus of Data which represents a rich source of

any usual or specific morphological aspect. In a second step, we expanded the perimeter by working on specific domain data from Corpus Nada having several properties. This data is organized in a data warehouse.

The second part of our Contribution in this work and shed light on the usefulness of working with Spark and Hadoop not as much as competitor but as accompanying to have better results in result accuracy and material convenience in the air of Big Data, so we proposed an improvement based on both Framework to make further optimizations on the algorithm of root removal of words and classification of its latest for analysis and decision-making in several areas.

REFERENCES

- [1] MAHDAOUY, ABDELKADER EL, ERIC GAUSSIER, ET SAID OUATIK EL ALAOU. EXPLORING TERM PROXIMITY STATISTIC FOR ARABIC INFORMATION RETRIEVAL . IN INFORMATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY (CIST), 2014 THIRD IEEE INTERNATIONAL COLLOQUIUM IN, 272277. IEEE, 2014.
- [2] "SOCIAL MEDIA USAGE IN MIDDLE EAST - STATISTICS AND TRENDS (INFOGRAPHICS)," GO-GULF, 4 JUN 2013. (ONLINE) . AVAILABLE: [HTTPS://WWW.GOGULF.COM/BLOG/SOCIAL-MEDIA-MIDDLE-EAST](https://www.gogulf.com/blog/social-media-middle-east) (ACCESSED NOVEMBRE 2014)
- [3] BUCKWALTER, T. QAMUS: ARABIC LEXICOGRAPHY [HTTP://MEMBERS.AOL.COM/ARABICLEXICONS/](http://members.aol.com/arabiclexicons/)
- [4] KHOJA, S. AND GARSIDE, R. STEMMING ARABIC TEXT. COMPUTING DEPARTMENT, LANCASTER UNIVERSITY, LANCASTER. INTERNET HOME PAGE, 1-7 (1999). [AVAILABLE AT: [HTTP://WWW.COMP.LANCS. AC.UK/COMPUTING/USERS/KHOJA/STEMMER.PS](http://www.comp.lancs.ac.uk/computing/users/khoja/stemmer.ps)]
- [5] GROLINGER, KATARINA; HAYES, MICHAEL; HIGASHINO, WILSON A.; L'HEUREUX, ALEXANDRA; ALLISON, DAVID S.; AND CAPRETZ, MIRIAM A.M., "CHALLENGES FOR MAPREDUCE IN BIG DATA" (2014). ELECTRICAL AND COMPUTER ENGINEERING PUBLICATIONS. PAPER 44.
- [6] BUDIMAN, R. (2013). UTILIZING SKYPE FOR PROVIDING LEARNING SUPPORT FOR INDONESIAN DISTANCE LEARNING STUDENTS: A LESSON LEARNT. *PROCEDIA - SOCIAL AND BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES*, 83: 5-10
- [7] A. NEHAR, , ATTIA, DJELLOUL ZIADI, HADDA CHERROUN, AND YOUNES GUELLOUMA. AN EFFICIENT STEMMING FOR ARABIC TEXT CLASSIFICATION. IN *INNOVATIONS IN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY (IIT)*, 2012 INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON, 32832. IEEE, 2012.
- [8] J. QIAN, D. MIAO, Z. ZHANG, AND X. YUE, "PARALLEL ATTRIBUTE REDUCTION ALGORITHMS USING MAPREDUCE," *INF. SCI. (NY)*, 2014.
- [9] https://hadoop.apache.org/docs/r1.2.1/hdfs_design.html, access, 2020
- [10] MUSTAFA (2013) MIXED-LANGUAGE ARABIC-ENGLISH INFORMATION RETRIEVAL. PHD THESIS, UNIVERSITY OF CAPE TOWN, CAPE TOWN.
- [11] DARWISH, K. AND MAGDY, W. (2014) ARABIC INFORMATION RETRIEVAL. *FOUNDATIONS AND TRENDS IN INFORMATION RETRIEVAL* , 7, 239-342. [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.1561/1500000031](https://doi.org/10.1561/1500000031)
- [12] MIRKIN, B. (2010) POPULATION LEVELS, TRENDS AND POLICIES IN THE ARAB REGION: CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES. ARAB HUMAN DEVELOPMENT, REPORT PAPER 1.
- [13] CHEUNG, W. (2008) WEB SEARCHING IN A MULTILINGUAL WORLD. *COMMUNICATIONS OF THE ACM*, 51, 32-40. [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.1145/1342327.1342335](https://doi.org/10.1145/1342327.1342335)
- [14] HABASH, N. AND RAMBOW, O. (2007) ARABIC DIACRITIZATION THROUGH FULL MORPHOLOGICAL TAGGING. *HUMAN LANGUAGE TECHNOLOGIES : THE CONFERENCE OF THE NORTH AMERICAN CHAPTER OF THE ASSOCIATION FOR COMPUTATIONAL LINGUISTICS*, ROCHESTER, 22-27 APRIL 2007, 53-56.
- [15] HEGAZI, N. AND EL-SHARKAWI, A. (1985) AN APPROACH TO A COMPUTERIZED LEXICAL ANALYZER FOR NATURAL ARABIC TEXT. *PROCEEDINGS OF THE ARABIC LANGUAGE CONFERENCE*, KUWAIT, 14-16 APRIL 1985.
- [16] MUSTAFA, M. AND SULEMAN, H. (2011) BUILDING A MULTILINGUAL AND MIXED ARABIC- ENGLISH COLLECTION. *3RD ARABIC LANGUAGE TECHNOLOGY INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE* , ALEXANDRIA, 17-18 JULY 2011, 28-37.
- [17] KADRI, Y. AND NIE, J.Y. (2006) EFFECTIVE STEMMING FOR ARABIC INFORMATION RETRIEVAL. *PROCEEDINGS OF THE CHALLENGE OF ARABIC FOR NLP/MT CONFERENCE* , LONDON, 23 OCTOBER 2006, 68-74.
- [18] ATTIA, M.A. (2008) HANDLING ARABIC MORPHOLOGICAL AND SYNTACTIC AMBIGUITY WITHIN THE LFG FRAMEWORK WITH A VIEW TO MACHINE TRANSLATION. PHD THESIS, THE UNIVERSITY OF MANCHESTER, MANCHESTER.

- [19] ATTIA, M.A. (2007) ARABIC TOKENIZATION SYSTEM. PROCEEDINGS OF THE 2007 WORKSHOP ON COMPUTATIONAL APPROACHES TO SEMITIC LANGUAGES : COMMON ISSUES AND RESOURCES , PRAGUE, 28 JUNE 2007, 65-72.
[HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.3115/1654576.1654588](https://doi.org/10.3115/1654576.1654588)
- [20] GOWEDER, A., POESIO, M., DE ROECK, A. AND REYNOLDS, J. (2005) IDENTIFYING BROKEN PLURALS IN UNVOWELISED ARABIC TEXT. PROCEEDINGS OF HUMAN LANGUAGE TECHNOLOGY CONFERENCE AND CONFERENCE ON EMPIRICAL METHODS IN NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING, VANCOUVER, 6-8 OCTOBER 2005, 246-253.
- [21] BUCKWALTER, T. (2004) ISSUES IN ARABIC ORTHOGRAPHY AND MORPHOLOGY ANALYSIS. PROCEEDINGS OF THE WORKSHOP ON COMPUTATIONAL APPROACHES TO ARABIC SCRIPT -BASED LANGUAGES , GENEVA, 28 AUGUST 2004, 31-34.
[HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.3115/1621804.1621813](https://doi.org/10.3115/1621804.1621813)
- [22] ALJLAYL, M. AND FRIEDER, O. (2002) ON ARABIC SEARCH: IMPROVING THE RETRIEVAL EFFECTIVENESS VIA LIGHT STEMMING APPROACH. PROCEEDINGS OF THE 11TH ACM INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON INFORMATION AND KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT , ILLINOIS, 4-9 NOVEMBER 2002, 340-347. [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.1145/584792.584848](https://doi.org/10.1145/584792.584848)
- [23] H S. BHOSALE¹, PROF. D. P. GADEKAR², A REVIEW PAPER ON BIG DATA AND HADOOP, INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC AND RESEARCH PUBLICATIONS, 4(10),2014.
- [24] LEKHA R.NAIR, DR. SUJALA,D.SHETTY, STREAMING TWITTER DATA ANALYSIS USING SPARK FOR EFFECTIVE JOB SEARCH, JOURNAL OF THEORETICAL AND APPLIED INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY ,. VOL.80. No. 2 2005 – 2015.
- [25] M. DHAVAPRIYA, N. YASODHA, BIG DATA ANALYTICS: CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS USING HADOOP, MAP REDUCE AND BIG TABLE, INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE TRENDS AND TECHNOLOGY (IJCST) – VOLUME 4 ISSUE 1, JAN - FEB 2016
- [26] REYNOLD XIN, JOSHUA ROSEN, MATEI, ZAHARIA, MICHAEL J. FRANKLIN, SCOTT SHENKER, ION STOICA. SHARK: SQL AND RICH ANALYTICS AT SCALE. SIGMOD 2013. JUNE 2013.
- [27] Y. SAMADI, M. ZBAKH AND C. TADONKI, "COMPARATIVE STUDY BETWEEN HADOOP AND SPARK BASED ON HIBENCH BENCHMARKS," 2016 2ND INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON CLOUD COMPUTING TECHNOLOGIES AND APPLICATIONS (CLOUDTECH), MARRAKECH, 2016, PP. 267-275. DOI: 10.1109/CLOUDTECH.2016.7847709
- [28] W. HUANG, L. MENG, D. ZHANG AND W. ZHANG, "IN-MEMORY PARALLEL PROCESSING OF MASSIVE REMOTELY SENSED DATA USING AN APACHE SPARK ON HADOOP YARN MODEL," IN IEEE JOURNAL OF SELECTED TOPICS IN APPLIED EARTH OBSERVATIONS AND REMOTE SENSING, VOL. 10, NO. 1, PP. 3-19, JAN. 2017. DOI: 10.1109/JSTARS.2016.2547020
- [29] M. U. ÇAKIR AND S. GÜLDAMLASIOĞLU, "TEXT MINING ANALYSIS IN TURKISH LANGUAGE USING BIG DATA TOOLS," 2016 IEEE 40TH ANNUAL COMPUTER SOFTWARE AND APPLICATIONS CONFERENCE (COMPSAC), ATLANTA, GA, 2016, PP. 614-618. DOI: 10.1109/COMPSAC.2016.203
- [30] SARD M, BUDI M, YU Y, BIRRELL A. DYRAD: DISTRIBUTED DATA-PARALLEL PROGRAMS FROM SEQUENTIAL BUILDING BLOCKS. 2ND ACM SIGOPS/EUROSYS EUROPEAN CONFERENCE ON COMPUTER SYSTEMS 2007. 2007. PP. 59–72.
- [31] A. VERMA, A. H. MANSURI AND N. JAIN, "BIG DATA MANAGEMENT PROCESSING WITH HADOOP MAPREDUCE AND SPARK TECHNOLOGY: A COMPARISON," 2016 SYMPOSIUM ON COLOSSAL DATA ANALYSIS AND NETWORKING (CDAN), INDORE, 2016, PP. 1-4. DOI: 10.1109/CDAN.2016.7570891
- [32] <https://www.infoq.com/articles/apache-Sparkintroduction>